

Mechanisms Underlying Catamenial Epilepsy

Bardia Haghighirad

School of Medicine, Trinity College Dublin – Dublin, Ireland

Trinity College Institute of Neuroscience, Trinity College Dublin – Dublin, Ireland

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ABSTRACT

Catamenial epilepsy is a condition that affects approximately 30% of women diagnosed with epilepsy, who experience cyclical exacerbation of seizures before, during and after the initiation of their menstrual cycles. Studies have shown that the seizures are caused by the fluctuations in the level of steroidal hormones such as estradiol, neurosteroids and progesterone. It has been evident that estradiol contributes to the excitation of CA1 pyramidal neurons in the hippocampus which leads to the occurrence of perimenstrual seizure exacerbations. Furthermore, studies have also shown that adrenergic neurosteroids such as testosterone, interfere with the ovarian cycle. Testosterone also, increases the chance of amygdala-kindled seizures and reduces the seizure threshold, and therefore, it leads to catamenial seizures. Researchers have now identified that a decrease in the level of progesterone before, during and after the initiation of the menstrual cycle, results in perimenstrual seizure exacerbation in women diagnosed with epilepsy, as in normal individuals, progesterone is converted to allopregnanolone which enhances the inhibitory effect of GABA on the receptor. While in most catamenial epileptic patients an increase of 50% in the medication is common, this literature, examines the effect of prolonged usage of cyclical progesterone therapy in women suffering from catamenial epilepsy.

Epilepsy was first introduced by John Hughlings Jackson in 1873 as the occasional, excessive, rapid, sudden and local discharges of the grey matter, linked to seizures [1]. Epilepsy can be defined as a progressive neurological disorder, associated with repetitive unprovoked seizures which can significantly affect an individual's quality of life [2]. The prevalence of epilepsy does not differ by either gender or age. However, it is projected that epilepsy affects 0.5%-1% of the world's population. Epilepsy may occur due to trauma to the brain, tumour growth, infection, stroke and also, by genetic factors known as idiopathic epilepsy. Of the patients treated with antiepileptic drugs (AED), 30% develop pharmacological resistance to current AED [3].

1.2. Types of Epilepsy

Epilepsy can be divided into two classes of partial seizures, involving only a specific part of the brain and generalized seizures, involving the whole brain area. In partial seizures, the discharges remain localized and therefore, the symptoms are dependent on part of the brain affected. Several symptoms of partial seizures include autonomic discharges, involuntary muscle movement and psychomotor epilepsy due to partial seizures in the temporal lobe. As mentioned previously, generalised seizures affect the whole brain area and the reticular system which results in excessive electrical activity between both hemispheres of the brain. The primary symptom in generalized seizures is an instant loss of consciousness. Moreover, generalized seizures can be divided into two types of tonic-clonic seizures and absence seizures. Tonic-clonic seizures involve excessive contraction of the musculature of the whole body, leading to muscle spasm in the whole body, which affects the thoracic region and therefore, stops

1. INTRODUCTION TO EPILEPSY AND CATAMENIAL EPILEPSY

1.1. Epilepsy history and prevalence

respiration in the individual's suffering from seizures [3].

1.3. Catamenial Epilepsy

Although epilepsy can be divided into different classes, one type that affects some women is known as catamenial epilepsy. Studies have shown that more than 30% of women that are in the reproductive age and have epilepsy will experience cyclical exacerbation of seizures that are align with their menstrual cycle. These seizures are associated with changes that occur in estrogen and progesterone serum levels throughout the menstrual cycle, leading to catamenial epilepsy. Nonetheless, the primary type of catamenial epilepsy is known as perimenstrual seizure exacerbation [4].

2. CAUSE OF CATAMENIAL EPILEPSY

2.1. Reproductive steroids leading to catamenial epilepsy

Furthermore, it has also been shown that the occurrence of epileptic seizures as well as perimenstrual seizure exacerbations is caused by reproductive steroidal hormones that contribute to neuroactivation due to their neuroactive properties. Example of such steroids include estradiol, progesterone and neurosteroids (*Figure 6.1*). Of the three steroids, progesterone is most involved in catamenial epilepsy, and this is further explain later in this literature [5].

2.2. Estradiol and catamenial epilepsy

Estradiol exhibits excitatory effects at the neural membrane which results in the activity of NMDA mediated glutamate receptors. NMDA stands for N-methyl-D-aspartate. Once the NMDA mediated glutamate receptors are activated, the resting discharge rate of the neurons is improved, in particular, in the hippocampus. More accurately, the excitation of the hippocampal CA1 pyramidal neurons is increased due to estradiol. This phenomenon occurs by post-transcriptional mechanisms. It is noteworthy to mention that rat estrous cycle studies have shown that the level of circulatory estradiol, positively correlates with the density of the dendritic spines on the CA1

pyramidal neurons. Consequently, estradiol can further enhance the CA1 pyramidal neurons excitatory inputs [6]. Moreover, the CA1 pyramidal neurons excitation is affected by estradiol by dependant mechanisms that are cytosolic neuronal estrogen receptor mediated. These receptors in the cortical and medial amygdaloid nuclei are abundant and they appear much less in the hippocampal pyramidal layers. Nonetheless, these estrogen receptors contain neurons that engulf with neurotransmitters such as GABA which is an inhibitory neurotransmitter. When genes that regulate the post-synaptic action are released and the activity of neurotransmitters are affected, estrogen, contributes to neuronal excitation which in turn increases the level of estradiol. Consequently, estradiol lowers the synthesis of GABA in the corticomедial amygdala which results in a lower inhibitory neurotransmission. The corticomедial amygdala is connected with the subcortical limbic forebrain structure and receives excess inputs from the brain stem monoaminergic and autonomic nuclei which sends axons towards the amygdala's central nucleus. This phenomenon occurs as the glutamic acid decarboxylase (GAD) activity is reduced [7]. Additionally, as the level of inhibitory neurotransmission is lowered, the epileptogenic muscarinic neurotransmission of the brain is increased via both acetylcholine and choline acetyltransferase [8]. It is worth stating that the exact role of estrogen in catamenial epilepsy is still unclear as studies have shown that the seizure threshold in the hippocampus is increased by estradiol, suggesting that estradiol may have neuroprotective properties in seizure induced injuries [5].

2.3. Neurosteroids and catamenial epilepsy

As previously mentioned, studies have shown that neurosteroids also play a significant role in the pathogenesis of catamenial epilepsy. Neurosteroids are a class of steroids, synthesized in the brain, which are involved in the continuous modulation of neuronal excitation as they target membrane receptors. Neurosteroids can be divided into three classes of I. Progesterone-derived neurosteroids such as allopregnanolone, II. Adrenal-derived neurosteroids, such as deoxycorticosterone (DOC) and III. Adrenergic neurosteroids, such as testosterone. Of the three classes mentioned above,

adrenergic neurosteroids are discussed in this literature [9]. Testosterone is an important prohormone and a circulatory androgen involved in the synthesis of neurosteroids. Testosterone can be found in the ovaries, and it acts as an estradiol synthesis precursor. The synthesis of testosterone in ovaries takes place in thecal interstitial cells, where it is later metabolised to estradiol via the granulosa cells. Similar to estrogen, it is believed that testosterone also interferes with the ovarian cycle. The pathway in which testosterone is metabolized to neurosteroids includes the estrogen pathway in which an enzyme known as aromatase, converts testosterone to estradiol which is then synthesized in the brain's peripheral tissue [10]. Previous studies have shown that androstenediol and androgenic neurosteroids influence the effect of testosterone on both seizure susceptibility and neuronal excitation. Having said that, testosterone increases the occurrence of amygdala-kindled seizures and pentylenetetrazol (PTZ) seizures and also, decreases the seizure threshold [11]. Consequently, testosterone aggravates catamenial seizure activity. This is due to an increase of up to 400% in testosterone secretion during ovulation [9].

2.4. Progesterone and catamenial epilepsy

Another important reproductive steroid hormone involved in catamenial epilepsy is progesterone, which plays a significant role in the pathogenesis of this condition. Progesterone exhibits anticonvulsive activities when converted to allopregnanolone. Allopregnanolone, binds to GABA type A receptor (GABA_A), which then improves the action of GABA on the receptor [12]. Studies have shown that neurosteroids withdrawal in women leads to perimenstrual seizure exacerbation, which results in GABAergic inhibition impairment. In addition, progesterone results in the activation of the progesterone receptors A and B (hPR-A and hPR-B). These receptors are ligand-activated transcription factors that are encoded by only one gene [13]. Once both progesterone receptors A and B are activated, they regulate gene expression as they localize to the nucleus. It is worth mentioning that both protein and mRNA of progesterone receptors A and B are located in the hippocampus pyramidal neurons and as stated previously, these pyramidal neurons are

associated in the progression and generation of catamenial epilepsy [14]. In a study conducted by Herzog et. al. 2007, it was shown that variations in progesterone levels during the menstrual cycle leads to the exacerbation of catamenial seizures in women with epilepsy. The study further showed that during the mid-luteal phase, the seizures decrease as the level of progesterone in the serum gets increased. Conversely, the study also showed that the seizures increase as the level of serum progesterone is decreased, indicating a higher estrogen to progesterone ratio [15]. Furthermore, other studies have also showed that a decrease in serum progesterone to estradiol ratio contributes to the pathogenesis of catamenial epilepsy. In a study conducted by El-Khayat and colleagues, 2008, it was shown that in women diagnosed with catamenial epilepsy, the level of serum progesterone at 9.4 ng/ml was lower in comparison with the control subjects where the serum progesterone levels were at 15 ng/ml. Nonetheless, the serum estradiol levels were similar in both groups. As a result, the study indicated an increase in estradiol to progesterone ratio in women suffering from catamenial epilepsy. It is noteworthy to mention that in women diagnosed with perimenstrual catamenial seizures, the serum progesterone levels were significantly lower at approximately 0.75 ng/ml in comparison with the control subjects where the serum progesterone levels were at 1.6 ng/ml [16]. Furthermore, the progesterone levels in patients suffering from luteal type seizures were lower at 2.7 ng/ml during the midluteal and at 0.6 ng/ml during the menstrual phase, in comparison with progesterone levels in patients experiencing non-catamenial seizures at 15.6 ng/ml and at 6.6 ng/ml in patients suffering from perimenstrual type seizures. These findings, however, indicate that fluctuations and disruptions in the ovarian cycle-related progesterone levels before, during and after the menstrual cycle, contribute to the pathogenesis of catamenial epilepsy in women. Consequently, there is a strong evidence indicating the potential in progesterone therapy for the treatment of this condition [16].

3. CLINICAL RELEVANCE OF CATAMENIAL EPILEPSY

3.1. The importance of cyclic progesterone therapy in catamenial epilepsy, a clinical study:

In a study conducted by Kim et. al. 2020, the effect of cyclic progesterone therapy for the treatment of catamenial epilepsy was assessed. This study contained two patients who were diagnosed with catamenial epilepsy, and they were treated during the luteal phase with cyclic progesterone therapy [17].

3.2. The effect of cyclic progesterone therapy on subject 1

Patient A was a 22-year-old female who was suffering from idiopathic generalized epilepsy and had normal brain MRI results. However, the EEG results showed a high-voltage spike and wave discharges. Levetiracetam was used to manage her symptoms where her symptoms appeared only twice a year. Until the age of 14, she had regular menstrual cycle. Nevertheless, she experienced absence seizures as well as generalized tonic seizures approximately twice per month as she got older. Both clobazam and topiramate were used, yet no effect was observed. Patient A experienced seizure attacks between 2-3 days after the beginning of the menstrual cycle and the seizures continued for one week after the initiation of her cycle. Medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA) 10mg tablets were given to patient A on the 14th to 28th day after the initiation of her cycle. After 12 consecutive months of MPA treatment, her catamenial epilepsy was treated and nevertheless, her habitual seizure occurrence did not change significantly (*Tables 6.1 and 6.2*)[17].

3.3. The effect of cyclic progesterone therapy on subject 2

Furthermore, patient B was an 18-year-old female who was suffering from juvenile myoclonic epilepsy and had normal brain MRI results. However, the EEG results showed frequent generalized bursts of high-voltage spike and wave discharges. Until the age of 11, she had regular menstrual cycles. Levetiracetam and sodium valproate were prescribed to patient B and resulted in the resolution of her generalized tonic-clonic seizures. Having said that, from 3 days prior and 3 days after the initiation of her menstrual cycle, she suffered from perimenstrual myoclonus exacerbations. Similar to patient A, therefore, she was given MPA 10 mg tablets, once per day for 12

consecutive months. During the follow-up examinations a year later, it was revealed that the frequency of her perimenstrual clustered myoclonus exacerbations were decreased significantly (*Tables 6.3 and 6.4*) [17].

4. CONCLUSION

Traditionally, catamenial epilepsy was treated by cyclic medications such as clobazam, acetazolamide and levetiracetam and also by an increase of up to 50% in the dosage form of the anticonvulsant given to the patient during the initiation of the menstrual cycle [18]. Several studies have shown that a decrease in progesterone level during the final stages of the cycle, increases the response to cyclic progesterone therapy in catamenial epilepsy [19]. Having said that, phase III clinical studies have not showed a significant difference between placebo and progesterone responders and yet, it is still believed that the effect of cyclic progesterone therapy is significant in comparison with progesterone therapy alone in the treatment of catamenial epilepsy [4]. Referring to the study conducted by Kim et. al. 2020, it can be concluded that prolonged cyclic progesterone therapy involving MPS 10 mg tablets once daily can significantly lower the frequency of the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle. Additionally, it can be further concluded that cyclic progesterone therapy is significantly effective in women suffering from perimenstrual seizure exacerbations [17].

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6. FIGURES and LEGENDS

Figure 6.1: Figure showing a summary of steroidal hormones that lead to catamenial epilepsy.

Table 6.1: Representing the seizure frequency in patient A, 3 days before and after the initiation of her perimenstrual cycle before the administration of MPA. This table is also showing a high frequency in the occurrence of catamenial epilepsy in this patient [17].

Seizure Frequency (Months of the year) Patient A Before Treatment	From 3 days before and three days after the initiation of the menstrual cycle	Non-menstrual cycle
1	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
2	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
3	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
4	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
5	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
6	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
7	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
8	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
9	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
10	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
11	-	-
12	-	-

Table 6.2: Representing the seizure frequency in patient A, 3 days before and after the initiation of her perimenstrual cycle after the administration of MPA. This figure is also representing a low frequency in the occurrence of catamenial epilepsy in this patient from the first month after treatment with MPA, indicating that MPA significantly reduces the occurrence of catamenial seizures and perimenstrual seizure exacerbation [17].

Seizure Frequency (Months of the year) Patient A After Treatment	From 3 days before and three days after the initiation of the menstrual cycle	Non-menstrual cycle
1	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
2	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
3	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
4	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
5	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
6	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
7	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
8	-	-
9	-	-
10	-	-
11	-	-
12	-	-

Table 6.3: Representing the seizure frequency in patient B, 3 days before and after the initiation of her perimenstrual cycle before the administration of MPA. This table is also showing a high frequency in the occurrence of catamenial epilepsy in this patient [17].

Seizure Frequency (Months of the year) Patient B Before Treatment	From 3 days before and three days after the initiation of the menstrual cycle	Non-menstrual cycle
1	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
2	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
3	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
4	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
5	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
6	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
7	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
8	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
9	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
10	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
11	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
12	-	-

Table 6.4: Representing the seizure frequency in patient B, 3 days before and after the initiation of her perimenstrual cycle after the administration of MPA. This figure is also representing a low frequency in the occurrence of catamenial epilepsy in this patient from the second month after treatment with MPA, indicating that MPA significantly reduces the occurrence of catamenial seizures and perimenstrual seizure exacerbation [17].

Seizure Frequency (Months of the year) Patient B After Treatment	From 3 days before and three days after the initiation of the menstrual cycle	Non-menstrual cycle
1	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
2	Catamenial Epilepsy	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
3	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
4	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
5	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
6	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
7	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
8	-	Non-Catamenial Epileptic Seizures
9	-	-
10	-	-
11	-	-
12	-	-